

Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW): Explainer & Timeline

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The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1979, is an international treaty that legally binds ratifying states to eliminate discrimination against women and ensure equal rights in political, economic, social, cultural, and civil spheres. Countries commit to enacting laws, policies, and education initiatives promoting gender equality. States parties must submit periodic reports on progress, and 114 have ratified the Optional Protocol (2000), enabling complaints from individuals or groups and inquiries about violations of the Convention. Although 189 countries have ratified or acceded to CEDAW, some have placed reservations that limit its application. Notably, the United States signed the treaty in 1980 but has yet to ratified it, and five UN member states – Vatican, Iran, Somalia, Sudan, and Tonga – have not signed. Despite ongoing legal and cultural challenges to its implementation, CEDAW remains a cornerstone of global efforts to advance women's rights and gender equality.

Key Details

Year : 1979 (Enforced 1981, optional protocol enforced 2000)

Duration : Indefinite

Legal Weight : Legally binding

Adoption : 6 Countries (Succession)

85 Countries (Accession)

98 Countries (Signed)

97 Countries (Ratified)

114 Countries (Ratified Optional Protocol)

Objectives :

Eliminate discrimination against women in all its forms.

Ensure full development and advancement of women in all fields.

Address de jure and de facto (by law, in fact) discrimination in all fields of life, including in the areas of politics, economy, society, culture, civil and family life (including sports).

Change social and cultural patterns and stereotyped roles of men and women.

Obligation, ensuring compliance and accountability through CEDAW procedures.

Definitions:

Accession:

The act whereby a state accepts the offer or the opportunity to become a party to a treaty already negotiated and signed by other states. It has the same legal effect as ratification. Accession usually occurs after the treaty has entered into force.

Ratification:

The international act whereby a state indicates its consent to be bound to a treaty if the parties intended to show their consent by such an act.

Succession:

The process by which a new state inherits the rights and obligations of a former state under a treaty, often after a territory changes hands.

Adoption:

The formal act by which the form and content of a proposed treaty text are established.

Triggers and Highlights

- 1946 to 1999 -

Political & Legal Protection of Women

Adoption of the Convention on the Political Rights of Women and the Convention on the Nationality of Married Women that focused on women's legal status and nationality independent of marital status, laid the groundwork.

International Women's Year

The UN proclaimed 1975 as the International Women's Year (IWY), which marked a high-visibility moment for women's rights globally.

Implementation Gaps & the Vienna Conference

The Conference acknowledged the need for new procedures to strengthen implementation of women's human rights and called on CSW and the Committee to 'quickly' examine the possibility of introducing the right of petition through the preparation of an Optional Protocol.

Establishment of the United Nations Commission on the Status of Women (CSW)

Created to monitor the situation of women and promote women's rights.

Concept of "women in development"

Recognising that development policies, economic growth and modernization had differential impacts on women, and that women's participation was essential.

Adoption of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW)

The international community responded to the accumulated insights, that women's rights needed more than legal statements — they needed enforceable obligations and a global standard.

Adoption of the Optional Protocol

Adopted in 1999 and entering into force in 2000, providing the means for individuals and groups to seek recourse and for the Committee to investigate grave or systematic violations of the Convention.

Key Articles Specific to Sport & Physical Education

Critical mentions in the treaty that categorically highlight women's participation in sport.

Direct Mentions

Indirect Mentions

About the Framework Explainer Series

An initiative of the Global Observatory to facilitate access to global and regional frameworks that impact gender and sport+.

About the Global Observatory for Gender Equality & Sport

The Global Observatory for Gender Equality & Sport is a global convenor and repository of research and expertise on gender equality and sport, physical education, and physical activity – or sport+ for short. The GO is creating a knowledge pool on women & gender related issues and bringing together diverse actors in sport in order to tackle them. The GO is an international NGO based in Lausanne, Switzerland. Established in July 2021 with the support of UNESCO and the Swiss Confederation, the GO is an initiative originated from UNESCO's 4th International Conference of Ministers and Senior Officials Responsible for Physical Education and Sport (MINEPS IV) in Athens, Greece, in 2003. The commitment to the GO was reinforced by the 2017 Kazan Action Plan (KAP) at MINEPS VI, in Kazan, Russia and further reaffirmed at MINEPS VII in Baku, Azerbaijan, in 2023, with support from over 100 member states.

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